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PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF KIDNEYS IN KIDNEY STONE DISEASES

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Abstract: In nephrolithiasis, the main pathological changes in the renal tissue are the development of dystrophic, necrobiotic changes in the cortical layer, which is the morphofunctional area of the kidneys, in the epithelia of the glomeruli, increased hydrostatic pressure in the renal plexus, and varying degrees of atrophy due to hemodynamic disorders in the kidneys. The initial changes include hyaline droplet dystrophy in the epithelia of the proximal tubules, condensation of protein substrates in the primary urine in the tubule lumen, condensation of mineral salts in the tubule lumen, and deposition of heavy metal salts and pigments in the renal tubules and calices.

Key words: nephrolithiasis, urolithiasis, kidney, pathomorphology, dystrophy, necrosis.

Urgency of the problem. It is the second most common urological disease in the world and affects every eighth person on earth, with an average of 1-20% of the population suffering from kidney stones. The incidence of kidney stones is 2 per 100 people in the 40-55 age group, and 1.7 per 100 people in the 56-74 age group. Geographically, kidney stones (urolithiasis) affect 8-15% of the population in the USA and European countries, 2-5% in Great Britain and Canada. In the Russian Federation, this figure is 10-23% of the population, and in the CIS countries, this figure is 13-50%. This indicates that the incidence of kidney stones and urolithiasis in Central Asian countries has increased by 12% over the past 10 years, confirming the urgency of the problem. In terms of kidney stones, the average incidence in the CIS countries among women of reproductive age is 23-31%, and the average incidence is 35-55 per 100,000 pregnant women, of which 15-28% lead to maternal death. Currently, the main causes of kidney stones are metabolic disorders, obesity, a sharp change in the ratio of macro and microelements in the diet, endocrine disorders, and a direct connection with chronic stress syndrome.

Currently, the increased incidence of urolithiasis among women of working age aged 21-40 years, kidney diseases, is one of the main issues in ensuring maternal and child health. This, in turn, indicates the urgency and high social importance of the problem.

The aim of the research is to study age-related pathomorphological and immunohistochemical changes in kidney dynamics in the development of urolithiasis in the population of Fergana region.

Material and methods: The material will be 73 kidney tissues from patients with kidney stones selected during 2022-2025 through biopsy and autopsy in patients treated for kidney stones at the Fergana branch of the RIUIATM. The tissues were stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Results and discussion: in our study, the main contingent of patients in the study was 14-44 and 45-59 years old. It was mainly found in women. In particular, microscopic examination revealed the accumulation of protein and heavy metal salts in the renal pelvis, the preservation of focal and chronic inflammatory infiltrates of flat epithelium on the surface of the calyx mucosa, metabolic calcinosis, and pigmentosis. The development of dystrophic, necrobiotic changes in the renal parenchyma and glomerular epithelium, the preservation of blood supply and drainage in the capillaries, and the formation of foci of hyaline droplet dystrophy and necrobiosis in the epithelium of the proximal tubules. As a result, dystrophic changes in all epithelia of the renal cortex were detected, leading to the deposition of complex compounds of coarse protein substrates, heavy metal salts, calcium, magnesium salts in the filtrated primary urine. At the same time, it was found that morphologically cholesterol deposits were formed, as a result of a sharp disruption of tubular epithelial reabsorption, a reduction in the transition period from primary urine to secondary urine, and various heavy-chain organic and inorganic salt compounds were deposited in the renal pelvis.

Conclusion

In nephrolithiasis, the main morphological substrate of the kidneys is dystrophic, necrobiotic changes in the epithelial cells of the renal parenchyma, increased hydrostatic pressure in the tubules, decreased primary urine reabsorption, and deposition of various substrates present in primary urine in the proximal and distal tubules in the renal pelvis and calyx. It was found that this occurs as a result of prolonged stagnation of urine in the kidneys under the influence of various etiologies: endocrinopathy, metabolic disorders, impaired mineral metabolism, pregnancy and other factors, with local dystrophic changes.

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